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Рахова Е.Э.	267
УЧЕНИЕ О ЦЕЛЬНОМ ЗНАНИИ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ И.В. КИРЕЕВСКОГО И В.С. СОЛОВЬЕВА	
Рўзиев Х.Б.	275
НЕКОТОРЫЕ СОВЕТЫ ПО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЮ ДИАЛОГОВ В УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ	
Таджиева М.Ф.	279
УЛУЧШЕНИЕ НАВЫКОВ ЧТЕНИЯ НАЧИНАЮЩИХ ИЗУЧАЮЩИХ АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК	
Тогаев Г.Э.	284
РОЛЕВАЯ ИГРА КАК СРЕДСТВО ИНТЕРАКТИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ	
Тоирова М.А.	289
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВОПРОСИТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЙ В «ПУТЕШЕСТВИЕ ГУЛЛИВЕРА» ДЖОНАТАНА СВИФТА	
Тураева Г.Х., Эштухтаров Н.Б.	294
ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИЕ ТРУДНОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ С АНГЛИЙСКОГО НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ	
Уролова О.П.	301
К ВОПРОСУ НАУЧНОГО ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ПОСЛОВИЦ	
Уролова О.П.	306
ПОСЛОВИЦЫ РАЗНЫХ НАРОДОВ О ЯЗЫКЕ	
Усмонова Ш.А.	308
КАК ОБУЧИТЬ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В РАЗЛИЧНЫХ УЧЕБНЫХ СТИЛЯХ?	
Усмонова Ш.А.	312
РОЛЬ ИГРЫ В МОТИВАЦИИ	
Хайитова Ф.А.	317
ОБУЧЕНИЕ НА ОСНОВЕ ПРОЕКТОВ И ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА	
Ходжаева Н.Т.	323
ОБУЧЕНИЕ АУДИТОРСКИМ НАВЫКАМ В СРЕДНИХ ШКОЛАХ	
Худоймуродова К.	327
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АСПЕКТ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНТОНАЦИИ НЕМЕЦКОГО ЯЗЫКА	
Щеглова М.И., Проходцев К.А., Добрынин А.С.	331
МИРОВОЗЗРЕНЧЕСКАЯ ФУНКЦИЯ ФИЛОСОФИИ	
Эсанов А.Ш.	335
ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МОДЕЛИ КОРДЕРА В АНАЛИЗЕ ОШИБОК УЧАЩИХСЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА	

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ

Мамараймова Д.Б.	344
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ	
Мамараймова Д.Б.	347
ПРИЕМЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА ПО КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ МЕТОДИКЕ	

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ЭСАНОВ АЗИЗБЕК ШЕРМАМАТ УГЛИ

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Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждается роль модели, предложенной английским лингвистом Corder S. Pit в анализе ошибок, относящихся к области анализа ошибок, которая является одной из основных отраслей английской лингвистики, в частности анализа ошибок учащихся иностранных языков. Там были допущены некоторые ошибки и недостатки узбекских студентов, которые анализируются по модели, которая показывает, насколько важна модель Кордера для устранения таких дефектов. В нем также резюмируется, что суждения о языковой компетенции учащихся иностранных языков, чей родной язык является узбекским, согласно анализируемым ошибкам через модель, которая может быть доработана.

Ключевые слова: ошибка, ошибка, анализ ошибок, модель Кордера, явные и скрытые ошибки, языковая компетенция.

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IMPORTANCE OF CORDER'S MODEL IN ANALYZING ERRORS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Annotation: This article discusses the role of the model proposed by the English linguist Corder S. Pit in analyzing errors that are relevant to the field of **error analysis** which is one of the major branches English linguistics, in particular the analysis of errors of foreign language learners. There given some errors and shortcomings made by Uzbek students which are analyzed through the model which reveals how important Corder's model is to fix such defects. It also summarizes that the judgments about the language competence of foreign language learners whose native language is Uzbek according to the analyzed errors through the model that can be further developed.

Key words: mistake, error, error analyze, Corder's model, overt and covert errors, language competence.

Pursuant to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On measures to further improve the system of foreign languages study" adopted on December 10, 2012, there launched new stage in both foreign language learning and teaching. Thanks to the great attention to this sphere, new modern methods and innovative technologies have been developed in recent years.

According to the modern principles of language learning and teaching, it is highly appreciated as an effective strategy in which both teachers and learners take equal responsibilities. In this process, the role of teachers is, surely, to urge their students to realize why they are learning the language or why they need it and to lead them till students get the needed target by the help of teachers in correcting their mistakes made in the process of learning, and to give them right and easy-follow instructions. In the

meantime the first task of students is to determine their own way of learning by making a clear imaginings about the language through the instructions of teachers. It is proved in the book *Methodology in language learning:*” The teacher has the role of facilitator – helping and encouraging learning to happen. He/she will not feel that learning can only happen as and when specific items are taught. Learners, too, must acknowledge that theirs is the more active role; they have to do the learning! They need to be aware of their own learning style and be willing to adapt and expand their learning strategies.”[1, 15]

For the reason that “learning a second language is a long and complex undertaking and it is not a set of easy steps that can be programmed in a quick do-it-yourself kit” [2, 1], it is important for both teachers and students to cooperate altogether during the learning process since there is always the need of analyzing the performance done by learners and of identifying how well they are performing. Naturally, while studying the second language, both the students and the language trainers face a great deal of difficulty. One of such problems is the errors and mistakes that eradicate during language study. The sophisticated aspect of this concern is that the mistakes of the language learners are not the same, and their roots are diverse. Besides, for the past few decades, many surveys, such as James (1998) [5], Tarone (1981) [6], Kleinmann (1977) [7] and Schachter (1974) [8], have shown that error analysis fails to account for the strategy of avoidance. A learner who for one reason or another avoids a particular sound, word, structure, or discourse category may be assumed incorrectly to have no difficulty therewith. The absence of error therefore does not necessarily reflect like native competence because learners may be avoiding the very structures that pose difficulty for them. In this sense, detection of defective errors and their identification are crucial in preventing similar errors and omissions that may occur in the learners’ further study. Since, it is stated as: “The best learning takes place when the learner is aware that the error has been made”. [4, 18] Today, thanks to the advance of language teaching systems and the use of various interactive innovative methods, there are a number of achievements in this field, that is, the analysis of errors. One of the most significant ones in this regard is undoubtedly the work to identify errors and integrate them into a single system. Through these achievements, errors and omissions in the language learning process of learners, whose

first language is Uzbek, can be further analyzed and utilized to improve language competency of learners. Since mistakes themselves can be a helpful tool for teachers and researchers in working out a clear justification about the errors done by learners, an English linguist Corder S. Pit once noted: “A learner's errors ... are significant in [that] they provide to the researcher evidence of how language is learned or acquired, what strategies or procedures the learner is employing in the discovery of the language”. [3, 167] As the term of “competence” is defined as following: “Competence includes a set of interrelated qualities of the person (knowledge, abilities, skills, methods of activity), asked in relation to a specific group of objects and processes, and necessary for quality productive activities”, the language competence of second language learners requires all features in the subject including information, cognitive, grammar and communicative competences. In assessing the language competency of learners who frequently make mistakes in their production of language, it is very difficult to sort out them due to the diversity of faults. And, as is stated above, integrating these errors in a system facilitates the assessment and judgment about learners. One of such systems we would like to analyze is the model for detecting errors proposed by the English linguist Corder S. Pit in 1971. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Procedure for identifying errors in second language production data (Corder 1971)

Analyzing and identifying errors of learners, we can determine how well they are acquiring the language and which parts of the language should be developed, in which learners mostly make mistakes. In this process, some crucial questions may arise: Do learners make mistakes due to a few temporary breakdowns in the process? Can that kind of imperfections be self-corrected? Or do they make errors owing to the lack of

knowledge which cannot be self-corrected? To find out answers and to infer how the learners' language competency is, we will analyze the following conversation according to this model to make a clear vision of how the model works:

Teacher: Good morning!

Learner: Good morning!

Teacher: Who are you? Or What is your name?

Learner: I am John.

Teacher: OK. What are you?

Learner: I am single. (1)

Teacher: Don't you understand me?

Learner: No, I understood you well. (2)

Teacher: I see. Can you play the piano?

Learner: No, I don't can play piano. (3)

Teacher: What about your sister?

Learner: Yes, she cans play piano. (4)

Teacher: You've made a mistake again.

Learner: Sorry, made I mistake? But if possible not stated in double-par you told me once not like a high wise.... (5)

It is obvious that the model is not complicated and depicts that teachers and researchers can easily follow the procedure. Then, we will consider the given examples of mistakes through the model:

(1) *I am single:*

A. Yes. The sentence is well formed in terms of grammar. However, it is a covert error which is correct at grammatical level, but not at discourse level according to the context.

B. No. (the sentence doesn't make sense in the context because the learner is being asked about his/her job but he/she understands the questioner that he is asking about his characteristics)

C. No. A plausible interpretation cannot be put on sentence in contex.

F. Yes. Uzbek

G. Yes. “Men bo`ydoqman”. A plausible interpretation can be put in terms of context.

H. The answer to the question “What are you?” should be such:

“I am a student”.

E. The question “What are you?” is misunderstood due to the false translation in Uzbek as “Siz qandaysiz?” or “Siz nimasiz?” Out₂

(2) *No, I understood you well.*

A. No. The sentence is not well formed in terms of grammar of the target level.

C. Yes. A plausible interpretation can be put on sentence in contex.

D. I understood you well.

E. The sentence reflect that the learner is in the language competence level in which all the verbs require post-posed –ed suffix to form past tenses. Lack of knowledge about irregular verbs. This is an overt error which is unquestionably incorrect at the grammatical level. Out₂

(3) *No, I don't can play the piano*

A. No. The sentence is not well formed in terms of grammar of the target level.

C. Yes. A plausible interpretation can be put on sentence in contex.

D. I can't play the piano.

E. The sentence contains the pre-posed don't auxiliary verb for negative sentence formation. Out₂

(4) *Yes, she cans play the piano.*

A. No. This sentence is not well formed in terms of grammar of the target level, either.

C. Yes. A plausible interpretation can be put on sentence in contex.

D. Yes, she can play the piano

E. This sentence also contains the incorrect usage of third-person singular instances with modals, which indicates that the learner has still not distinguished modals from other verbs. Out₂

(5) *Sorry, made I mistake? But if possible not stated in double-par you told me once not like a high wise....*

- A. No. This sentence is not well formed in terms of grammar of the target level
- C. No. A plausible interpretation cannot be put on sentence in context.
- F. Yes. Uzbek.
- G. No. this sentence cannot be translated literally into L1.

Out₃

It is obvious that the model is not complicated for teachers and researchers that they can easily follow from one step to another. This simple analyze on the mistakes and errors made by a beginner level learner presents the importance of Corder's Model in error analyze which can help teachers and researchers to determine how to solve the problems in learning second language at the early stages of learners by judging what kind of mistakes appear most as it enables them to presume what sort of corrections and instructions should be developed through this model. Moreover, this model is important for the assessment of second language learners as mistakes and errors analyzed through the model reveal the portion of the learners' competence in the target language which defines in what degree they are and what kind of corrections they must take. In the given examples, it becomes clear that Uzbek learners usually tend to make mistakes and errors related to the following issues:

- incorrect use of auxiliaries in negative and interrogative sentences. This is because there is no auxiliary verbs in the Uzbek language and they are new for them which brings discomforts resulting in an overuse of auxiliaries for every negative and interrogative sentences no matter if they are models or main verbs;

- incorrect use of adding the third person suffixes “-s/-es”. After learning the rules of verb forms in Present tense, there appears such a notion that every verb after third person subjects should take “-s/-es” suffixes, even modals, as well;

- lack of knowledge about modal verbs due to fact that there is no modals in Uzbek which are a separate group of verbs serving to add extra meanings to main verbs. In the Uzbek language there is a type of verbs called assisting verbs which are considered as components of complex verbs. Modals can be taught as their equivalents in the process of teaching the language;

- misuse of past tense forms of verbs. As in the English language there are two types of verbs in the Past which are regular and irregular verbs whereas there is no in Uzbek, this causes learners not to be able to distinguish these verbs.

Certainly, since the roots and reasons of errors are diverse, samples of such shortcomings are abundant. However, it is important to know that “there is a danger in too much attention to learners' errors. While errors indeed reveal a system at work, the classroom language teacher can become so preoccupied with noticing errors that the correct utterances in the second language go unnoticed. While the diminishing of errors is an important criterion for increasing language proficiency, the ultimate goal of second language learning is the attainment of communicative fluency”. [2, 218] Thus, instead of being preoccupied with finding errors, it is necessary for teachers to develop the ways in which foreign language learners can freely and easily master their knowledge. By being aware of their own mistakes in the correct way through such models, students can improve their language competency without being worried about making mistakes.

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